

EFFECTS OF HYGROTHERMAL AGING ON THE DURABILITY OF GLASS/EPOXY COMPOSITES. PHYSICO-CHEMICAL ANALYSIS AND DAMAGE MAPPING IN STATIC FATIGUE

A. Chateauminos¹, B. Chabert², J.P. Soulier², L. Vincent¹

1- Ecole Centrale de Lyon - Département Matériaux-Mécanique Physique
U.R.A. CNRS 447 - BP 163 - 69 131 ECULLY CEDEX - FRANCE

2 - Université Claude Bernard- Laboratoire d'Etudes des Matériaux Plastiques et Biomatériaux
U.R.A CNRS 507 - 43, bd du 11 Novembre - 69622 VILLEURBANNE CEDEX - FRANCE

ABSTRACT

Hygrothermal aging effects on the static fatigue (i.e. relaxation) of a glass/epoxy composite have been investigated. From both the in-situ analysis of damage mechanisms and physico-chemical data, it was possible to plot the lifetimes of the aged material in damage maps. Different damage areas which are characterized by different failure mechanisms were considered. Moreover, each of these damage areas was delimited by a set of parameters which are representative of the individual fatigue behaviour of the matrix, the fibre and the interface.

Keywords : Glass/epoxy composite ; static fatigue ; hygrothermal aging

1 INTRODUCTION

In the course of normal service life, structural composites are subjected to both mechanical loading and environmental exposures including at least temperature and humidity. As a result, extensive studies have been carried out over the past few years on the environmental effects on composite materials. A great deal of experimental evidence has been adduced to demonstrate that hygrothermal aging strongly affected both physico-chemical and thermomechanical properties of composites. However, relatively few studies are concerned with environmental effects on fatigue properties in relation to aging mechanisms.

The goal of this study was thus to establish correlations between the changes in fatigue behaviour of a glass/epoxy composite and the hygrothermal degradation of each of the material constituents (fibre, matrix and interface). During water exposure, three major kinds of aging processes are susceptible to act :

- reversible plasticization of the epoxy network resulting from water diffusion,
- macroscopical damage such as matrix cracking and/or fibre/matrix debonding,
- loss of bearing properties of the glass reinforcement due to chemical attack.

The effects of these processes on the fatigue behaviour have been investigated by two different approaches :

- a physico-chemical approach involving the analysis of the material viscoelastic behaviour in relation with water diffusion,
- a mechanical approach focused on the identification of the damage initiation and propagation processes during static fatigue (i.e. relaxation). This paper is focused on this latter aspect.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2-1 Sample preparation

The material studied is an unidirectional glass/epoxy composite. The epoxy matrix was based on a DGEBA (CIBA LY 556) resin cured with 26 parts per hundred DDM (CIBA HT 972). The reinforcement was P9HT high strength R-Glass fibres (1600 tex roving) supplied by Vetrotex, France. Unidirectional plates were obtained by filament winding. The impregnation was performed at 65°C without any solvent. The cure cycle was 3 hours at 80°C followed by 3 hours at 175°C. The volume fraction of fibre was 0.48 and the void content less than 0.1. The plates were cut into coupons 10 mm wide and 70 mm long using a diamond coated slitting wheel with water cooling.

2-2 Environmental exposure

Preliminary moisture diffusion experiments were carried out in distilled water at 30°C, 50°C, 70°C and 90°C. The results, which have been reported elsewhere¹, were used to establish aging conditions for the fatigue tests. Two different conditioning treatments have been considered in this study:

i) an un-aged state obtained by conditioning the as received samples in a vacuum oven at 70°C until they reach a constant. This state was considered as the reference state.

ii) an aged state resulting from the exposure of the dried material to distilled water at 30°C, 50°C, 70°C and 90°C for 100 days. Whatever the temperature, this immersion time has been found to be sufficient enough to provide a water content close to the Fickian saturation level.

2-3 Static fatigue

The static fatigue behaviour ($R = \epsilon_{\min} / \epsilon_{\max} = 1$) was investigated using a three point bending test. The specimens were characterized at imposed deflection on specific test devices, a span to depth ratio of 20 being selected in order to minimize shear stresses. Samples were loaded at 2 mm/min until a given strain value ϵ_{\max} . The stiffness loss was then continuously measured by a load cell beneath the loading nose. In-situ observation of the tensile side of the specimen was performed using transmission microscopy. The bending cell was designed so that the specimens could be fully immersed during the test.

Static fatigue tests on the un-aged material were performed in room conditions (22°C, ± 50 R.H.). Aged samples were tested in distilled water at 22°C in order to prevent moisture desorption during the fatigue test.

A 10% stiffness loss was selected as a conventional failure criteria, the beginning of the loading being chosen as the time origin. For a more convenient comparison with dynamic fatigue (see below) the lifetimes t_{10} were normalized by the loading time ($t_{10}^* = t_{10} / \text{loading time}$).

3 RESULTS

3-1 Damage mechanisms

3-1-1 Un-aged composite

By in-situ analysis of the the tensile side of the un-aged specimens during the static fatigue test, it was possible to distinguish between two damage steps :

i) a first step related to the delocalized multiplication of non interactive defects. For the composite considered, these defects were mainly broken fibres which appeared as randomly distributed dark points on the tensile side of the specimens (fig. 1a). Stress concentration at the vicinity of the broken ends of the fibres often resulted in the nucleation of a matrix crack. It must be emphasized that this fibre breakage started well below the ultimate bending strain of the composite, due to the statistical distribution of the fibre strength. Damage evolution during fatigue loading will thus be governed by the local tolerance of the composite to these first nucleated defects.

During this first stage, stiffness losses can thus be considered to be due to both fibre breakage and viscoelastic relaxation of the matrix. After a rapid decrease, stiffness loss curves tend to stabilize (fig.2a) indicating that the number of created defects remain constant and that they did not propagate.

ii) the second step was related to the progressive propagation of a localized damage on the tensile side of the specimens. From the first nucleated defects, a few cracks grew perpendicular to the fibre direction. This damage propagation involved matrix cracking, fibre breaking and interfacial shear failure at the crack tip (figure 1b). During this second stage, the observed continuous stiffness loss (fig.2a) has been found to be correlated to the total length of the cracks on the tensile side of the specimen².

(a) Delocalized fibre breakage

(b) Localized progressive cracking during damage propagation

Fig.1 : Damage mechanisms in bending static fatigue
(tensile side of the specimen)

3-2-2 Aged composite

After water exposure, no qualitative change was noted during the first damage step. On the other hand, the damage propagation step was significantly affected by the immersion at 90°C. Progressive localized cracking gave way to a drastic tensile failure characterized by a sudden drop in the stiffness loss curves (fig.2b) without any previous macroscopic damage. The first step (delocalized multiplication of broken fibre) thus occupied the overall lifetime of the material.

Fig. 2 : Stiffness loss curves before and after water aging at 90°C ($\epsilon_{\max}=0.75 \epsilon_R$)

3-2 S-T diagram

All the fatigue results have been reported in a S-T diagram giving the imposed strain ϵ_{\max} versus the normalized lifetime t^*_{10} . It can be noted that aging induced a significant decrease in endurance properties. For the considered exposure time, this decrease is strongly dependent on aging temperature even if the relative weight gain M_t remains approximatively the same. Moreover, a great scatter in the lifetime was obtained after exposure at 90°C. As it was not observed for the other exposures, this scatter can be considered as representative of the intrinsic fatigue behaviour of the material at this temperature. It can also be associated to the change from progressive to non-progressive damage after exposure at 90°C.

Except at 90°C, all the fatigue data can be fitted using a Wöhler type relation similar to those obtained for bending dynamic fatigue of glass/epoxy composites³ :

$$\epsilon_{\max} = A - B \text{Log } t^*_{10} \quad (1)$$

The decrease in endurance properties was also associated to a decrease in monotonic properties². Initial strength and strain to failure were not recovered after drying the composite, thus indicating that the loss of mechanical properties can be attributed to the irreversible nucleation of hygrothermal defects. In order to correlate this evolution to the weakening of each of the composite constituents, fatigue data were reported in "damage maps" inspired by the fatigue-life diagrams introduced by Talreja⁴.

Fig. 3 : Fatigue-life diagram in static fatigue before and after aging

3-3 Damage maps in static fatigue

Considering dynamic tensile fatigue, Talreja mainly considered two damage areas in S-N diagrams (fig.4a):

(i) a horizontal band centered about the composite strain to failure ϵ_R which corresponds to fibre breakage and the resulting interfacial debonding at the broken ends of the fibres. In this area, failure is considered to result from delayed fibre breakage until a cross section is stressed high enough to break the remaining fibres in it. Damage is thus considered as non-progressive nature because it does not involve the progressive growing of a damaged area on the overall fatigue life.

(ii) the second damage area is a sloping band located between the lower boundary of the fibre breakage scatter band and the horizontal line corresponding to the fatigue limit of the matrix ϵ_m . This region corresponds to progressive matrix cracking and interfacial shear failure.

Fig. 4 : Damage maps

Similar diagrams can be plotted for static fatigue by taking into account the following modifications (fig.4b):

(i) the upper part of the diagram will not be centered about ϵ_R , but around the A parameter defined in Wöhler's relation (1). It is due to the fact that the lifetime criterion selected for static fatigue is not a failure criterion as is the case for tensile fatigue. A can be defined as the strain level which induces 10% stiffness loss immediately at the end of the loading ($t^*_{10}=1$). On the other hand, ϵ_R is defined as the strain value corresponding to the maximal load on the load/deflection curve obtained during monotonic characterization. However, a proportionality has been found between A and the monotonic failure strain measured at the same loading rate as for the fatigue test³. It can thus be assumed that A also characterizes the non-progressive part of the damage and is representative of the fibre breakage mechanisms at the considered loading rate.

(ii) The lower boundary for the progressive propagation of a localized damage can not directly be set as the fatigue limit ϵ_m of the unreinforced matrix. This limit, denoted as ϵ_s , is defined by the resistance to crack propagation from the first defects (broken fibres) created during the loading. The propagation or the non-propagation of such a progressive damage will a priori be dependent on two factors :

- the intrinsic resistance of the unreinforced matrix to cracking (defined by ϵ_m),
- the interfacial shear strength. Two situations can schematically be considered at the crack tip :

There is no debonding and stress concentration at the crack tip induces fibre breaking and subsequent matrix cracking.

If some debonding occurs, the resulting local stress accommodation could result in crack arrest and no progressive damage propagation will be observed.

As mentioned above, ϵ_s must thus be considered in terms of tolerance to the first created defects. Moreover, such a limit clearly appears as strongly dependent on the interfacial shear strength of the composite.

3-4 Effects of aging on damage maps

Damage maps after water aging can also be plotted by considering the following effects (fig.5):

(i) the decrease in A value due to the reduced strength properties of the glass fibres after water aging. For example, a decrease of 25% in the strength of the used R-Glass monofilaments has been found after 100 days aging in distilled water. Also reported for E-glass fibres, this loss of bearing properties has been attributed to flaws creation on the glass surface, due to a thermally activated ion exchange mechanism^{5,6}.

(ii) The shift to short times of the progressive damage sloping band must also be taken into account. This evolution has been found to be due to both an enhanced cracking rate during step II and to a reduced duration of the step I. Both effects can be considered as due to an increased number of defects after aging. However, no crack could be detected on micrographs of the aged composite and viscoelastic analysis did not reveal any irreversible decrease in the matrix crosslink density¹. It can therefore be assumed that the hygrothermally induced defects are mainly fibre or interfacial defects. The increased cracking propagation rate can especially be considered as resulting from the increased probability of finding a defect in the part of the fibre located at the crack tip.

(iii) Concerned with ϵ_s , two processes must be taken into account :

- the beneficial effect of the hygrothermally induced debonding on crack propagation. Interfacial degradation of the composite considered has been previously studied by both sorption/desorption experiments and viscoelastic analysis. The results, which have been reported elsewhere², showed that interfacial debonding was enhanced at the most elevated immersion

temperatures (70°C and 90°C). Stress accommodation at the crack tip by debonding will thus take an increased role at these temperatures.

- the effect of network plasticization on the intrinsic resistance of the matrix to cracking. Due to an enhanced creep ability^{7,8}, stresses at the crack tip will be able to relax more easily thus decreasing the cracking rate. The extent of plasticization effects in relation to water diffusion can be measured by the decrease in Tg following water immersion. For the considered epoxy matrix, the Tg of the wet composite has been found to be linearly related to the water content M_t , this relationship being independent on the immersion temperature¹.

After 100 days of aging, the water contents of the composite are approximately the same whatever the immersion temperature. Plasticization effects on crack propagation will thus be identical and can not explain the change in damage mechanism observed at 90°C.

Fig. 5 : Damage map after 100 days of aging at 50°C and 90°C

The change from progressive to non-progressive damage at 90°C can be attributed rather to the lowering of A value below the limit strain ϵ_s . Defects (broken fibres) thus can be initiated but they can not propagate because $\epsilon_{max} < \epsilon_s$. As a result, sites of fibre break will be scattered randomly in the composite without matrix cracking. Due to delayed fibre breakage, the probability of finding a section weakened enough to break will increase with time, leading to the final failure of the sample. Scatter in lifetimes is thus representative of the statistical distribution of fibre failure strain ϵ_f after aging.

4- CONCLUSION

Static fatigue behaviour of glass fibre/ epoxy composites has been investigated during water aging between 30°C and 90°C. Hygrothermally induced defects resulted in a temperature dependent decrease in fatigue properties. This lowering was associated with a transition from progressive damage to non-progressive damage after exposure at 90°C. The analysis of aging effects has been undertaken by the way of damage maps. Different damage areas were considered which are characterized by either progressive or non-progressive propagation. Each of these damage areas was delimited by a set of parameters (A, ϵ_s , ϵ_m , ϵ_f) which are representative of the individual fatigue behaviour of each of the composite constituents. It has been concluded that the damage map evolution upon aging involved mainly the loss of static properties of the glass fibres and an enhanced interfacial degradation at 90°C.

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